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World experience in ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy

Abstract: The author of the article substantiates the methodological and applied nature of world experience in ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy. The processes of identification of priority industries, sectors of the economy in the world economy are considered. The purpose of the article is to scientifically substantiate the theoretical and methodological aspects of the formation of world experience in ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy. To perform the tasks in the research process used general and special methods – theoretical generalization, grouping, historical knowledge, systems design. The works of Y. Berezhivskyi, O. Ilyash, P. Kutsyk, R. Lupak, and T. Vasylytsiv were used to study the problems of ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy. Scientific works of researchers allow to understand the sources of experience, features and tools, conclusions for public policy to ensure the development of priority sectors of the economy. The author identifies aspects of strategy and planning, formation and implementation of structural policies for the development of priority sectors of the economy in some highly developed countries. It was possible to characterize the conceptual provisions for improving the management system of strategic sectors of the economy at the level of countries with a high level of technological potential. According to the world experience, the tools of economic support of formation and intensification of development of priority branches of economy are offered.

Key words: priority sectors of the economy, public policy, national economy, structural policy, development, governance.

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Мировой опыт обеспечения развития приоритетных отраслей экономики

Аннотация: Автор статьи обосновывает методико-прикладный характер мирового опыта обеспечения развития приоритетных отраслей экономики. Рассматриваются процессы идентификации приоритетных отраслей, секторов экономики в мировом хозяйстве. Целью статьи является научное обоснование теоретико-методических аспектов формирования мирового опыта обеспечения развития приоритетных отраслей экономики. Для выполнения поставленных

задач в процессе исследования использовались общенаучные и специальные методы – теоретическое обобщение, группирование, историческое познание, системное проектирование. Для исследования проблем обеспечения развития приоритетных отраслей экономики использовались труды Ю. Березовского, О. Иляш, П. Куцика, Р. Лупака, Т. Васильцова. Научные труды исследователей позволяют понять источники формирования опыта, особенности и инструментарий, выводы государственной политики обеспечения развития приоритетных отраслей экономики. Автором определены аспекты стратегирования и планирования, формирования и реализации структурной политики развития приоритетных отраслей экономики в отдельных высокоразвитых странах. Удалось охарактеризовать концептуальные положения усовершенствования системы управления стратегическими отраслями экономики на уровне стран с высоким уровнем технологического потенциала. Согласно мировому опыту, предложен инструментарий экономической поддержки становления и активизации развития приоритетных отраслей экономики.

Ключевые слова: приоритетные отрасли экономики, государственная политика, национальное хозяйство, структурная политика, развитие, управление.

Introduction

The study and elaboration of foreign experience of state policy of development of priority sectors of the economy is of significant strategic importance, as it allows to draw conclusions about wrong scenarios and practices (and this is a way to eliminate potential risks and threats), as well as tools and measures that have had positive consequences, in particular, regarding the state of development (at the start) of industries, financial and resource capabilities of the state, the action of external and internal factors, selected vectors and strategic political and economic guidelines of the country, etc.

The purpose of the article is to scientifically substantiate the theoretical and methodological aspects of the formation of world experience in ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy.

The objectives of the article were to study the priority sectors of the economy to determine the methodological and applied nature of world experience in development, identification of economic sectors, strategy and planning, formation and implementation of structural development policy, improving institutional management, formulating tools to support economic development and development control.

To perform the tasks in the research process used general and special methods – theoretical generalization (to determine the content characteristics of the development of priority sectors of the economy), grouping (to substantiate the conceptual characteristics of the development and implementation of state policy to ensure the development of priority sectors of the economy in different countries), historical knowledge (while studying specific world experience in the development of priority sectors), system design (to develop proposals for development of priority sectors) economy).

The study of world experience is an important foundation for building methodological and conceptual support of public policy, because it develops, clarifies, and finally confirms the existing theoretical and methodological developments in this case in the field of state regulation of sectoral economic systems. Key aspects of the implementation of state policy to ensure the

development of priority sectors of the economy are highlighted in the works of scientists: O. Amosha, O. Berezina, V. Gamaliy, O. Ilyash, Yu. Kindzersky, P. Kutsyk, R. Lupak, O. Nosyrev, G. Ortina, L. Peltek, O. Pischulina, M. Siruk, T. Shtets, V. Tochilin, T. Vasylytsiv.

Since, we do not reject the methodological and applied nature of the generalization of world experience in terms of formation and improvement of methodology for analyzing and evaluating the safety of priority industries and the quality and effectiveness of policies to strengthen it.

Thus, it is a study aimed at further implementation in Ukraine of progressive foreign practices in the areas:

- identification of strategic industries, sectors of the economy;
- strategy and planning, formation and implementation of state structural policy;
- improving the system of organization and management of priority sectors of the economy;
- formation of tools for economic support of their formation and intensification of development;
- defining mechanisms for monitoring and controlling the development of strategic industries

Identification of priority industries, sectors of the economy

In terms of identifying priority sectors of the national economy, in foreign practice in almost all countries, and world leaders – on the spot, much attention is paid to the defense industry, which is logical, because it is, first, the key to military security; secondly, a significant part of GDP and exports, often high-tech products (services) (*Vasylytsiv, Lupak, 2017:105-112*). The most striking examples here are the effective functioning of the State Agency for Defense Industry of Turkey, the General Directorate of Armaments of France, the US Department of Defense and others (*Siruk, 2021*). In South Korea, the priority sectors of the economy are semiconductors, shipbuilding, automotive, metallurgy and light industry; in France – automotive, nuclear and space technology, eco-industries, fashion industry (*Amosha O., 2013:24-28*).

In the current conditions of globalization and active development of information and communication technologies, total digitalization of society, administrative services and business, objectively intensified trends in many countries (Ukraine is no exception) regarding the state policy to stimulate the digitalization sector. In fact, the ICT industry, which produces technologies related to the creation, storage, transmission, processing and management of information that serves as a locomotive for the spread of digitization processes (*Kutsyk et al, 2020:65-70; Vasylytsiv et al, 2020:14-19*). The created IC products have their application far beyond this type of economic activity, respectively, actualizing public and private support for projects and platforms for the development and implementation of IT products (services).

That is why among the strategic priorities of economically developed European countries are the development of Big Data and Internet of Things (Belgium), improving the infrastructure of ICT and digital economy (Spain, Italy), nano and micro technologies, robotics, cybersecurity, cloud computing, robotics (Germany), improvement of all economic systems on the basis of ICT (Poland), support of e-mobility, e-health, e-education, unified digital platforms (Portugal), digital technologies in prevention and treatment, management of functioning of settlements (France, Finland) (*Smart Specialisation Platform, 2021; Shtets et al, 2020:14-19*).

Thus, the priority sectors of the economy include those related to aspects of national defense

and security, allow to realize the economic potential of the country, ensure balanced development of the national economy, promote the identity of the nation.

Strategies and planning, formation and implementation of structural policy for the development of priority sectors of the economy

The urgency of the state policy of regulating the development and realization of the potential of priority sectors of the national economy is recognized at the highest level of many countries, as evidenced by the functioning of the executive bodies of the relevant structures responsible for this task. There is also known experience when in some countries institutions were created with a clear functional purpose to manage the development of specific industries, sectors, areas (directions) of the national economy. Thus, in Japan, to implement the national strategy *Society 5.0*, a Strategic Growth Council was formed, formed of representatives of government, business and science. 4 strategic spheres of the country's progress and their modernization on the basis of digitalization were identified. These are healthcare, mobility, infrastructure and digital financial technologies (*Pischulina, 2020:74-100*).

Institutional support of the state policy to promote the development of priority sectors (spheres) of the economy and public life also extends to its institutional and legal plane. To this end, the United States has passed the law *On Smart Cities and Communities*, the bill *On Access of Municipalities to Smart Technologies in Infrastructure* is being discussed. The laws clearly institutionalize the four vectors of public policy tools. First, it is the coordination of the activities of government agencies at different levels in the formation and implementation of policies for sustainable smart-oriented development of territories and conglomerations; secondly, the maximum spread of ICT, provided that a high level of data security is guaranteed. Third, the development of a system of administrative services provided to the population and businesses (*Smart Cities and Communities Act, 2019*).

Another aspect is the improvement of the institutional and organizational system to support the functioning and development of priority sectors of the national economy. In the context of the example of European policy for the development of smart-oriented types and areas of economic activity, such elements of institutional infrastructure as factories of the future, digital innovation hubs, technology centres of key additional technologies, European Institute of Technology, joint research centres and others were created (*European Commission, 2021*). In fact, they acted as the institutional platforms on the basis of which the interests of all stakeholders in activating and spreading the digital transformation of the economy were united using the tools of public-private partnership (in all areas – financial, organizational, technological, informational, innovative, etc.). and society, the creation and implementation of smart technologies for sustainable development.

Thus, the development of priority sectors of the economy involves the development and implementation of strategies and programs for regional and sectoral development; adherence to a systematic approach to planning based on a combination of the formation of new industries, sectors, sustainable and smart-oriented development of territories; promote the identity of the nation.

Improving the system of organization and management of strategic sectors of the economy

In the world practice other approaches to planning, and further-realization, of such policy are applied also. For example, the approach currently being implemented in the EU in terms of ensuring smart-oriented regional development can be considered largely innovative. According to the strategic plan, the regions of the EU countries must form strategies for their development in accordance with their smart specialization, focused on identifying and realizing the internal potential of innovative competitive development, strengthening interregional cooperation (*European Commission, 2021*). As a result, today all regions of the EU have their own strategy and smart specialization programs. In general, their number exceeds 120 and they contain specific mechanisms, tools and means of development of industries, economic activities, areas that ensure the spread of technological innovation, digital transformation of economic and social sectors, advanced ICT in housing and communal services, facilities social and other infrastructure (*Berezina, 2018:35-38; Lupak et al, 2021:855-864*).

Smart-oriented development strategies are adopted not only at the level of countries and regions. This practice is widespread at the city level. Currently, smart development strategies are being implemented in cities such as Barcelona, Vienna, Stockholm, Leipzig, more than 13 cities in Germany and 20 in the United Kingdom. The strategies provide a wide range of tools to support business and community projects in the areas of safety, time and convenience, health, environmental quality, social cohesion and social inclusion, employment, and living wage growth (*Zigurat Global Institute of Technology, 2019*).

The economic tools of state policy to stimulate the development of priority sectors of the economy are quite extensive. In this sense, we are talking about a set of regulatory measures, usually combined into the industrial policy of the state, as strategic industries in line with the trends of industrialization and the current reindustrialization of national economies (*Berezinskyi, 2021:825-836; Lupak, 2017:117-123*). There are approaches to the clear institutionalization of state industrial policy (Japan, France, Germany, Italy and other countries) in the form of eponymous laws, strategies, programs, etc., and to its implementation without excessive declaration and separation in a separate direction (USA, UK).

Thus, the development of priority sectors of the economy implies the presence in the structure of central and local executive power of the body coordinating the policy of development of priority sectors; creation of specialized government structures responsible for various functional aspects of supporting basic industries, sectors; adoption of laws, etc. NPA on state regulation of development of priority industries; development of infrastructure for the development of basic sectors of the economy.

Tools for economic support for the formation and intensification of the development of priority sectors of the economy

We note the main models of state policy to stimulate the development of priority, strategic sectors of the national economy – export-oriented, import substitution and innovation, when the first measures are implemented mainly financial and investment support for the production and export potential of certain industries; for the second – protectionist instruments to curb the entry of goods into the domestic market, in the production of which the country has domestic potential; on the third – the formation of R&D infrastructure and providing economic support for the introduction of technological innovations and ensuring technological competitiveness as

a leading condition for the development of priority sectors of the national economy (*Ortina, 2016; Lupak, 2017:39-45*).

Despite the basicity of these models, the world's leading economies use different combinations of more specialized economic instruments. For example, Japan – selective sectoral programs, fiscal and economic incentives within the framework of structural policy, antitrust policy (*Government of Japan, 2013*); USA – lending to projects for technological modernization of production, stimulating the placement of low-tech production units abroad to reduce labour and resource capacity, export licenses and patents, a system of interconnected and reinforcing measures of tax, monetary, innovation, investment, structural policy (*Nasyrev, 2017:29-32*); South Korea – implementation of specialized regional programs to support the development of strategic industries with high potential in a given area (*Kindzersky, 2013:40-44*); Western European countries – instruments of decentralization and strict control over the state of competition in the markets, levers of tax, budget, monetary policy, small business development, simplification of permitting procedures and increasing the investment attractiveness of integrated sectoral property complexes (*Pelteke, 2010:151-162*).

The world experience of the state economic policy of stimulating the development of smart infrastructure is quite rich. Again, this is a combination of sectors of the real sector of the economy (e.g., ICT) and other sectors of society (such as housing and communal services, medicine, education, environmental protection, energy, transport and communications, etc.). Thus, in order to establish Industry 4.0 on the basis of the Internet of Things and robotization of production, the German government has allocated funds to finance research and development of 72 test laboratories – small and medium-sized businesses (*Lab Network Industrie 4.0, 2021*). Sweden has introduced a system of fiscal incentives for businesses that implement projects for digital business transformation for the development of sustainable industrial production (*Ministry of Enterprise and Innovation of Sweden, 2016*). In the Netherlands, at the expense of the government created and operate the so-called field digital laboratories, whose task is to support enterprises of the real sector of the economy in conducting experiments on the development, testing and implementation of solutions for business digitization and development of the smart industry (*Lab Network Industrie 4.0, 2021*). In 2017, the UK government decided to invest 2.4% of GDP for 10 years in the creation and operation of centres – platforms for cooperation between businesses, representatives of the research sector, inventors, owners of industrial property, and also the development of digital infrastructure (*GOV.UK, 2021*).

Thus, the development of priority sectors of the economy involves the formation of healthy competition, proactive antitrust policy; stimulating the development of SMEs in basic economic activities; improving the investment environment in priority areas; implementation of a set (system) of tools to stimulate the development of priority sectors for all components of economic policy.

Mechanisms for monitoring and controlling the development of priority sectors of the economy

At present, the practice of monitoring the development of priority industries has become quite common. However, in international practice it is not accepted to conduct analysis and diagnosis from the standpoint of the functioning and development of a particular industry. In

contrast, the approach is used when such conclusions are made from the standpoint of the result obtained in the country's economy as a result of the implementation of effective structural policies and stimulating growth in basic economic activities, areas and sectors of the national economy (*Gamaliy et al, 2016:3-10; Tochilin et al, 2009:23-38; Iyash et al, 2020:95-113*). Relevant reports are based on the analysis of rating positions, as well as values of indices and sub-indices of international ratings of technological readiness and level of innovative development of the Global Competitiveness Index of the World Economic Forum, technological infrastructure of the World Competitiveness Index of the Institute for Management Development in Switzerland, digital competitiveness of the Institute for Management Development in Switzerland, innovations of the International Business School INSEAD, innovative potential of the European Business School, innovative development of Bloomberg, knowledge economy of the World Bank Institute, competitiveness of talents, protection of property rights, etc.

On the other hand, there are also known practices when to fully monitor the state of the situation, websites (digital platforms) are created, which display all the information on the formation and implementation of public policy in strategic areas of the national economy. For example, this is how the European Union's Smart Specialization Platform works, with a total of 19 EU Member States and 7 non-EU countries, as well as 178 EU and 30 non-EU regions; more than 180 smart specialization strategies at the regional and national levels are presented (*Smart Specialisation Platform, 2021*).

Thus, the development of priority sectors of the economy involves monitoring structural development through indices of technological readiness and level of innovation development, technological infrastructure and digital competitiveness, knowledge economy, etc.; creation of web pages for presentation of development strategies / programs and control of their implementation.

It is expedient to disseminate this type of experience in the case of planning, implementation and control of the course and effectiveness of state policy to ensure the development of priority economic activities. Since, other aspects of foreign experience should be taken into account in the form of conclusions of state policy to manage the development of priority sectors of the national economy (*Fig. 1*).

Discussion

In any strategy to ensure the development of priority sectors of the national economy by the state in developed economies, systematic work is being done to create favourable conditions to ensure security, especially financial, increase activities and strengthen competitive positions of strategic industries in domestic and foreign markets. Such a policy is called structural, industrial, security, sectoral, sectoral, technological, etc. and its formation begins with the identification of priority sectors for the national economy.

The criteria for identification are mainly:

- 1) ensuring the sustainable functioning and development of society (in the context of the implementation of functions equated to national security);
- 2) available economic, natural resource, geopolitical potential (in the context of using the competitiveness of the economy);
- 3) situational advantages that open up in domestic and foreign markets (in the context of using

- the opportunities provided by the current situation);
- 4) the ability to serve as a foundation for integration, support for the development of most sectors of the national economy, the general stabilization of the economic and social situation in the country;
 - 5) representation of the cultural and national identity of the country.

Conclusion

Thus, the world experience shows different forms and methods of state structural policy in line with the formation, ensuring the effective functioning, realization of economic resources and export potential, balanced development of priority sectors of the national economy.

The world experience has developed a set of effective tools and means of public policy, which are important to implement and coordinate with the peculiarities of national practice in the areas of:

- strategy and planning, formation and implementation of state structural policy;
- improving the system of organization and management of priority sectors of the economy;
- formation of tools for economic support of their formation and intensification of development;
- definition of mechanisms of monitoring and control of development of strategic branches, realization of their potential in the system of national economy.

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Appendix

Sources of experience	Features, tools used	Conclusions for public policy
<p>✓ Identification of priority industries, sectors of the economy</p>	<p>Selection of industries that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - related to aspects of national defense and security of society; - allow to realize the economic potential of the country; - ensure the balanced development of the national economy; - promote the identity of the nation 	<p>Definition and <i>normative-legal consolidation</i> of the list of priority types of economic activity, sectors and branches of economy;</p> <p><i>formation of organizational and managerial system</i> of state management of development of basic branches;</p> <p><i>availability</i> of a system of mutually agreed <i>sectoral, operational and strategic program documents</i> for the development of</p>
<p>✓ Strategy and planning, formation and implementation of structural policy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - development and implementation of strategies and programs for regional and sectoral development; - adherence to a systematic approach to planning based on a combination of new industries, sectors, sustainable and smart-oriented development of territories 	<p>priority sectors of the economy, which are adjusted in real time and consistent with internal and external realities;</p> <p><i>subordination</i> of all components and elements of <i>the state economic policy on formation of conditions</i> for effective functioning and development,</p>
<p>✓ Improving the system of organization and management of strategic sectors of the economy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the presence in the structure of central and local executive power of the body coordinating the policy of development of priority industries; - creation of specialized government structures responsible for various functional aspects of supporting basic industries, sectors; - development of infrastructure for the development of basic sectors of the economy 	<p>realization of potential of priority branches of economy;</p> <p><i>ensuring the flexibility of structural policy</i> in accordance with changes in domestic resource opportunities, the situation in foreign markets and global economic trends;</p>
<p>✓ Tools for economic support for the formation and intensification of the development of priority industries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - formation of healthy competition, proactive antitrust policy; - stimulating the development of SMEs in basic economic activities; - improving the investment environment in priority areas; - implementation of a set (system) of tools stimulating the development of priority sectors for all components of economic policy 	<p>establishing a <i>system of monitoring, analysis, control and responsibility</i> of the subjects of structural policy implementation</p>
<p>✓ Mechanisms for monitoring and controlling the development of priority industries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - monitoring of structural development through indices of technological readiness and level of innovative development, technological infrastructure and digital competitiveness, knowledge economy, etc.; - creation of web pages for presentation of development strategies / programs and control of their implementation 	

Figure 1. The results of generalization of world experience in ensuring the development of priority sectors of the economy